

1 Article

2 InSAR-based mapping to support decision-making 3 after an earthquake

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29 **Abstract:** It has long been recognized that earthquakes change the stress in the upper crust around
30 the fault rupture and can influence the behaviour of neighbouring faults and volcanoes. Rapid
31 estimates of these stress changes can provide the authorities managing the post-disaster situation
32 with valuable data to identify and monitor potential threads and to update the estimates of
33 seismic and volcanic hazard in a region. Here we propose a methodology to evaluate the potential
34 influence of an earthquake on nearby faults and volcanoes and create easy-to-understand maps for
35 decision-making support after large earthquakes. We apply this methodology to the Mw 7.8, 2016
36 Ecuador earthquake. Using Sentinel-1 SAR and continuous GPS data, we measure the coseismic
37 ground deformation and estimate the distribution of slip over the fault rupture. Then we use this
38 model to evaluate changes of static stress on the surrounding faults and volcanoes and produce
39 maps of seismic and volcanic activity likelihood. We found in general good agreement between
40 our maps and the seismic and volcanic event occurred after the Pedernales earthquake. We
41 discuss potential and limits of the methodology

42 **Keywords:** InSAR; Sentinel-1; GPS; Ecuador earthquake; stress changes; active faults; volcanoes;
43 decision-making

44

45 1. Introduction

46 Earthquakes influence the crust around them, changing the stress state and influencing the
47 faults and volcanoes in the vicinity [1,2]. This can result in an increase in seismicity and volcanic
48 activity in areas of stress build-up [3]. Faults interaction by the static stress transfer have been
49 demonstrated in numerous studies in the last decades, including the occurrence of aftershocks (e.g.
50 [4-7]), the triggering of earthquakes in nearby faults or segments [8,9] or in the far field related to
51 dynamic triggering [10,11], and the occurrence of volcanic eruptions or episodes of volcanic unrest
52 after an earthquake [12,13]. Similarly, the volcanic processes can change the stress state on its
53 vicinity interacting also with active faults. As a consequence of these interactions and changes in the
54 stress state of the crust large earthquakes modify the seismic and volcanic hazard in its vicinity.

55 Space geodesy is now routinely used following an earthquake to image the displacement of the
56 ground and estimate the rupture geometry and the distribution of slip over the fault rupture
57 surface (e.g. [14-17]). Using the obtained source model, it is possible to evaluate the remaining
58 seismic moment deficit and to infer the stress changes on nearby faults and volcanoes produced by
59 the earthquake, which can be used to identify which faults and volcanoes are brought closer to
60 failure or activation.

61 In recent years, several initiatives that use Earth Observation data to provide support to
62 authorities managing the post-earthquake scenario have developed:

- 63 • The International Charter Space and Major Disasters [18]: an international consortium
64 including resources of fifteen space agencies that quickly provides satellite-derived
65 imagery and supplemental information to any country that requires assistance in
66 response to major disasters.
- 67 • The UNAVCO consortium (<http://www.unavco.org/>) that supports geodetic networks
68 and provides free and open geodetic data to help with preparedness and mitigation of
69 hazards
- 70 • The ARIA project (<https://aria.jpl.nasa.gov/>) which is a collaboration between JPL and
71 Caltech to exploit geodetic and seismic observations in support of hazard response.
- 72 • The Geohazards Exploitation Platform (GEP) of European Space Agency (ESA)
73 (<https://geohazards-tep.eo.esa.int/>) that support the exploitation of satellite EO for
74 geohazards
- 75 • The LiCS project (<http://comet.nerc.ac.uk/COMET-LiCS-portal/>) that map tectonic
76 strain from Sentinel-1 InSAR and uses the results to model seismic hazard.

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78 The influence of an earthquake in nearby faults and volcanoes can be evaluated through
79 different methods (see for example [19] and references therein). The Coulomb failure stress criterion
80 is one of the most common analyses used to explain fault interactions and seismological
81 observations after earthquakes, such aftershocks distributions (e.g. [7,8]).

82 Although these procedures are commonly used today by the academic community, the
83 transference of these results to the authorities managing the post-earthquake situation is not
84 straightforward and thus its usefulness is reduced in practice. Providing comprehensible maps to
85 the final user is a pending task.

86 Here we propose a methodology to evaluate the potential influence of an earthquake on
87 nearby faults and volcanoes and create easy-to-understand maps for decision-making support after
88 an earthquake. We apply this methodology to the Mw 7.8, 2016 Ecuador earthquake. Using
89 Sentinel-1 SAR and continuous GPS data, we measure the coseismic ground deformation and
90 estimate the distribution of slip. Then we use this model to calculate changes of stress on the
91 surrounding faults and volcanoes. The results are compared with the seismic and volcanic events
92 that have occurred after the earthquake. We discuss the potential and limitations of the
93 methodology and the lessons learnt from discussion with local authorities.

94 2. Study area

95 The Pedernales earthquake occurred in the Ecuadorian subduction zone, where the Nazca and
96 South American plates converge at 55 mm/yr [20,21]. The earthquake took place on 2016 April 16 at

97 23:58:36.980 UTC (<https://earthquake.usgs.gov/earthquakes/eventpage/us20005j32#origin>) at $20.6 \pm$
 98 3.2 km depth (Fig. 1) and the focal mechanism is consistent with the rupture of the subduction
 99 interface between the Nazca and South American plates. The studies published to date reveal that
 100 the Pedernales earthquake ruptured a 100-120 km long segment of the subduction interface and
 101 consisted of two main asperities [28,29].
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104 **Figure 1.** Reference map of our study area in Ecuador (red box in the inset map). The relative
 105 Nazca–South American convergence rate and direction are shown with a black arrow [20] and the
 106 location of the trench is shown with a heavy black barbed line. The black dashed box shows the
 107 region in Figs 2 and 3. The location of the continuous GPS sites used in this study is shown as blue
 108 inverted triangles. The Global CMT focal mechanism of the 2016 Pedernales earthquake is shown.
 109 The topography and bathymetry are from the ETOPO1 1 arc-minute global relief model [22]. The
 110 green segment indicates the approximate rupture area of the 1906 earthquake [23] and the red
 111 semi-transparent areas represent the rupture areas of the 1942, 1958 and 1979 earthquakes [24–27].

112 The relative movement of the plates produces $M > 7.5$ earthquakes (Figure 1) such as the M_w 8.8
 113 1906 Ecuador – Colombia earthquake, that ruptured a large region of 500 km of the subduction
 114 interface [30] and the sequence of earthquakes that partially ruptured the same area between 1942
 115 and 1979 (Fig. 1). The 2016 Pedernales earthquake seems to have ruptured a similar area than the

116 1942 earthquake [29]. Apart from megathrust earthquakes, the subduction process is responsible for
117 the uplift of the Andean range [31], crustal faults on the upper plate and Quaternary volcanism [32].
118 Continental Ecuador is divided into several morphostructural regions from west to east: the
119 Coastal plain, the Cordillera Occidental, the Cordillera Oriental and the upper Amazon basin.
120 Active tectonics is dominated by large faults [33] that separate different tectonic regimes including
121 the coastal region, where the subduction of the Carnegie Ridge and the oblique subduction control
122 active structures, the North Andean Block, limited by a NNE dextral strike-slip fault system and the
123 Eastern Andean Frontal fault zone that limits the North Andean block along the Subandean region.
124 These crustal faults are capable of producing earthquakes, such as the 1987 Ms 6.9 earthquake [34].
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126 3. Data and Methods

127 3.1. GPS displacements

128 We processed daily RINEX data from 28 cGNSS stations from the Continuous
129 Monitoring GNSS Network (REGME) in Ecuador. We estimated the site coordinates before and
130 after the mainshock of the 16 April 2016, Mw7.8 Pedernales Earthquake by using Bernese GPS
131 Software version 5.0 [35], and calculated coseismic displacements by taking the differences between
132 the daily site coordinates. The data were processed on a daily basis using the Bernese Processing
133 Engine (BPE), which applies a double-difference
134 processing strategy. We applied IGS precise orbits and earth orientation parameters, with an
135 absolute antenna phase center and a FES2004 ocean tide-loading model [36]. Only observations
136 made above an elevation cut-off angle of 5° were used to estimate parameters, and
137 an elevation-dependent weighting was applied. The tropospheric effect was
138 modelled on a prior dry-Niell [37] model and completed by estimating zenith delay corrections for
139 each site at 1-hour intervals using the wet-Niell mapping function. The ambiguity resolution is
140 based on the Quasi-Ionosphere-Free (QIF) baseline-wise analysis. Baselines were constructed based
141 on a strategy of maximum observations.

142 In order to establish a link with the global reference frame ITRF2008 (IGb08), we use 17
143 continuously recording GPS stations from the International GNSS Service (IGS) network. Once
144 obtained the daily solutions and coordinates of REGME stations, we imposed "a
145 posteriori" constraints on implementing the chosen reference frame. The coordinates of the IGS
146 stations were constrained (NNT- No Net Translation option) to their ITRF2008 values.

147 3.2. InSAR displacements

148 We processed Interferometric Synthetic Aperture Radar (InSAR) data from the European Space
149 Agency (ESA) Sentinel-1 satellite to estimate the coseismic line-of-sight (LOS) ground motion.
150 Using the Sentinel-1 processor developed at the CTTC (<http://geomatics.cttc.es/remote-sensing/>), we
151 combined 2 Sentinel-1 images from descending relative orbit 40, with dates 12 April 2016 and 24
152 April 2016. The 3-arcsec resolution NASA Shuttle Radar Topographic Mission (SRTM) DEM [38]
153 was used to remove the topographic phase contribution. The interferogram was filtered using a
154 power spectrum filter [39] and unwrapped using the MCF method [40]. The interferogram was
155 geocoded and rectified with a 90 m resolution.

156 3.3. Modeling the earthquake source

157 We first downsample the InSAR data using a quadtree approach (e.g. [41] which samples the
158 data according to their spatial variance, leaving more data in regions of high phase gradient near
159 the source. After downsampling, the original ~235000 data are reduced to ~2000 points.

160 We build the geometry of the subduction interface based on the global subduction zone model
161 of [42] at the latitude of the Pedernales earthquake. We divide it into an array of 450 elements, each
162 measuring 10 km along strike and 10 to 14 km along dip, with a variable dip that increases with
163 depth from 10° to 30°. We solve for the slip distribution along the 450 patches using a least-squares

164 minimization with the non-negativity constraint on the slip. We impose the rake of 123° (from the
 165 focal mechanism, <http://earthquake.usgs.gov/earthquakes/eventpage/us20005j32#origin>). To limit
 166 oscillations of the solution, we impose some smoothing on the solution, by minimizing the
 167 second-order derivative of the fault slip (e.g. [43]).

168 3.4. Estimation of static stress changes

169 To estimate the static stress changes induced by the Pedernales earthquake we use Coulomb failure
 170 stress change (ΔCFS) analysis (e.g. [8,44]). This takes into account the shear and normal stress
 171 changes ($\Delta\tau$ and $\Delta\sigma$) induced by the earthquake on selected surfaces or receivers, such as faults or
 172 dikes, considering and apparent friction coefficient (μ') to infer the total coulomb stress, using the
 173 equation:

$$\Delta CFS = \Delta\tau - \mu' \times \Delta\sigma$$

174 The Coulomb stress change was calculated using Coulomb 3.4 [45] assuming an elastic
 175 isotropic halfspace characterized by a Young modulus of 30 GPa and Poisson ratio of 0.25. The
 176 apparent (or effective) friction coefficient used for the receiver surfaces is 0.4.

177 We use the coulomb criteria to estimate the variation of stress induced by the Pedernales
 178 earthquake on three different receivers:

- 179 • Potential continental faults: we first select the faults from the catalogue of active faults in
 180 Ecuador of [46]. We classify the main sets according to the type of fault: normal, reverse and
 181 strike-slip faults. Additionally, we plot the frequency distribution of fault orientation in rose
 182 diagrams. In total, the database shows 278 faults, indicating the fault length, slip direction,
 183 plunge of the slip vector and slip type, among others parameters. For each subset of faults we
 184 extract average values of strike, dip, and rake; which are used as receiver fault orientations. We
 185 compute stress changes on each fault subset.
- 186 • Known fault traces: from the active faults database of [46] we extracted the fault traces and
 187 obtained points spaced 1 km apart along them. Then we estimate the Coulomb failure stress
 188 change induced by the Pedernales earthquake on those points with the correspondent
 189 potential rupture orientation characteristics (strike,dip,rake), at 5 km depth.
- 190 • Subduction interface: Using the geometry of the subduction interface from [42] we extract the
 191 strike, dip and rake of each node and estimate the Coulomb failure stress change induced by
 192 the Pedernales earthquake on each node.
- 193 • Volcanoes: we used the Ecuadorian volcanoes with historic activity from The Global
 194 Volcanism Program database (http://volcano.si.edu/search_volcano.cfm). We select a set of five
 195 currently active volcanoes, which have been extensively studied and extract the orientation of
 196 their magma paths, using the criteria of [47] and references therein. We then estimate an
 197 average orientation that is used to calculate the induced normal stress change ($\Delta\sigma$) on the
 198 volcano magma pathway. Positive values on a particular volcano indicate unclamping
 199 produced by the 2016 earthquake, which indicates dilatation in the crust at the depth of the
 200 magma chamber. In this case, the magma pathway is affected by a normal stress reduction or
 201 unclamping and this might promote new volcanic eruptions (e.g. [48]). We model the normal
 202 stress change at different depths, ranging from 0 to 10 km.

203 3.5. Final maps

204 To produce the final maps we simplify the different maps obtained from the stress change
 205 analysis to produce more easy-to-understand maps. We use a traffic light colour coding (red,

206 yellow, green) with three possible values to classify the volcanic and tectonic elements according to
207 the likelihood of their activation by the Pedernales earthquake. We produce four different maps:

- 208 • Map of continental faults: We integrate the six different maps of Coulomb stress changes over
209 the correspondent six fault subsets into one map of average positive stress change. We classify
210 the final ΔCFS values obtained in three values of seismic activity likelihood and colour the
211 final map using those values: green (low likelihood) indicates areas with $\Delta CFS < 0.1$ bar,
212 yellow (medium likelihood) indicates areas with $0.1 \text{ bar} \leq \Delta CFS \leq 1 \text{ bar}$ and red (high
213 likelihood) indicates areas with $\Delta CFS > 1 \text{ bar}$.
- 214 • Map of active fault traces: We classify the final ΔCFS values obtained over each fault trace in
215 three values of seismic activity likelihood of the fault segment activation. Then fault traces are
216 coloured according to those values: green (low likelihood) indicates faults with $\Delta CFS < 0.1$ bar,
217 yellow (medium likelihood) indicates fault segments with $0.1 \text{ bar} \leq \Delta CFS \leq 1 \text{ bar}$ and red (high
218 likelihood) indicates faults with $\Delta CFS > 1 \text{ bar}$
- 219 • Map of the subduction interface: We classify the final ΔCFS values obtained over each node of
220 the subduction interface in three values of seismic activity likelihood and colour the final map
221 using those values: green (low likelihood) indicates areas of the slab with $\Delta CFS < 0.1$ bar,
222 yellow (medium likelihood) indicates areas with $0.1 \text{ bar} \leq \Delta CFS \leq 1 \text{ bar}$ and red (high
223 likelihood) indicates areas with $\Delta CFS > 1 \text{ bar}$.
- 224 • Map of volcanoes: We classify the final $\Delta\sigma$ values obtained for the average orientation of the
225 volcanoes magma paths in three values of volcanic activity likelihood and colour the final map
226 according to these values: green (low likelihood) indicates volcanoes with $\Delta\sigma < 0.01$ bar,
227 yellow (medium likelihood) indicates volcanoes with $0.01 \text{ bar} \leq \Delta\sigma \leq 0.1 \text{ bar}$ and red (high
228 likelihood) indicates volcanoes with $\Delta\sigma > 0.1 \text{ bar}$. The difference in $\Delta\sigma$ values at depths 0 – 10
229 km is almost identical due to the distance between the Pedernales earthquake source and the
230 volcanic arc (~ 300 km), and therefore we only represent the value estimated at 10 km depth.

231 4. Results

232 4.1. GPS and InSAR displacements

233 The coseismic interferogram (Fig .2) shows a lobe of ground deformation moving away from
234 the satellite (colour blue-green), which is located to the left of the image (red arrow labelled LOS in
235 Fig 2). Maximum displacement is ~ 80 cm of movement away from the satellite. This interferogram
236 covers a period of 12 days (from 12 to 24 April 2016.), and thus it can also include, apart from
237 deformation associated to the Pedernales mainshock, deformation occurred during the 8 days after
238 the earthquake.

239 Continuous GNSS data recorded displacements with almost 70 cm of horizontal trenchward
240 motion and subsidence of more than 17 cm near the town of Pedernales (PEEC station, see Fig. 2).
241 The sites located near the coast also show subsidence, with areas of uplift found at inland stations
242 (QVEC, ABEC, CXC, QUEM).

243 The displacement field observed with both InSAR and GPS data is consistent with onshore
244 ground deformation commonly observed in subduction earthquakes, characterized by subsidence
245 and horizontal trenchward motion (ground experiencing uplift is closer to the trench and often
246 under the ocean).

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Figure 2. Coseismic displacement field from InSAR and GPS data. In the coseismic interferogram (wrapped), each colour fringe represents 2.8 cm of displacement in the line-of-sight direction. The white arrow indicates satellite Line-of-Sight direction (LOS) and satellite azimuth (Az). Black and blue arrows represent GNSS horizontal (black arrows) and vertical (blue arrows) displacements estimated from the Continuous Monitoring GNSS Network (REGME) in Ecuador, before and after the 16 April 2016, Mw7.8 Pedernales Earthquake. The 95% confidence ellipses for each GNSS stations are shown.

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4.2. Earthquake source from InSAR and GPS data

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According to our best model, the Pedernales earthquake ruptured a 100-km-long segment of the subduction interface and most of the slip (slip larger than 2 m) occurred between depths of 13 and 30 km (Fig. 3). The equivalent geodetic moment of our model, considering a shear modulus of 3.3×10^{10} Pa, is 5.63×10^{20} Nm (Mw 7.77), which is consistent with seismological estimates (Mw = 7.8). Slip maxima (asperities) locate in two main areas separated by a lower slip region (<2 m), in agreement with previously published models [28,29,49]. Supplementary Fig. S1 and S2 show GPS and InSAR residuals corresponding to this model.

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Figure 3. (a) Coseismic slip distribution on the subduction interface from inversion of Sentinel-1 and GPS data. Colours show the magnitude of slip in metres.

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4.3. Faults and volcanoes selected for this study

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The result of the analysis of active faults of Ecuador is shown in Figure 4. The 278 faults of the [46] catalogue can be divided into six families: Two sets of normal faults, oriented N45°E and N320°E, two sets of reverse faults oriented N350°E and N15°E, right-lateral strike slip faults N60°E trending and left-lateral strike slip faults that exhibit a conjugate set, N80°E and N330°E (Supplementary Table S1). Furthermore, the total length of each fault type is a relevant parameter to be considered in this analysis. In the case of reverse faulting, fault set with N15°E trending is the 85% of the reverse faulting for fault length larger than 10 km.

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Figure 4. Rose diagrams of the frequency of faults orientation according to the fault type, extracted from the Ecuador Active Faults database of [46]. (a) Normal faults, two main sets with NE- and NW trending; (b) Reverse faults, showing a main orientation towards NNW; (c) Right Lateral strike-slip, with a main direction of NE-trending; (d) Left lateral strike slip faults with two conjugate sets, NW-SE and ENE-WSW trending faults. In (c) and (d), arrows indicate the sense of the movement for strike slips; (e) Fault segments (green lines) from the Ecuador Active Faults database of [46]. Holocene volcanoes from http://volcano.si.edu/search_volcano.cfm are shown as red symbols.

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The compilation of information on the selected volcanoes (Tungurahua, Guagua Pichincha, Reventador, Sangay and Cotopaxi) revealed that most of them have vertical or sub-vertical magma

284 paths, with NE-SW azimuths in most of them (see Supplementary Table S2). We use this average
 285 orientation to estimate the induced normal stress change ($\Delta\sigma$) on each volcano magma pathway.

286 4.4. Results of the static stress analysis

287 We have produced 9 maps of static stress changes corresponding to the 6 crustal faults
 288 families, the subduction interface, the average stress increment taking into account all the fault
 289 families and the Ecuadorian volcanoes (Fig. 5). We have produced the same set of maps using the
 290 Global CMT focal mechanism with rupture dimensions obtained from [50] empirical relations
 291 (Supplementary Figure S4).

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Figure 5. Coulomb failure stress changes induced by the 2016, Mw 7.8 Pedernales earthquake on: (a-f) different faults sets with strike-dip,rake (according to the right hand rule and the rake with the

295 Aki and Richards convention): (a) N15-35,90; (b) N 45-85,180; (c) N195-35,90 (d) N230-75,90; (e)
296 N110-75,-90; (f) N320-89,0; (g) Coulomb failure stress change on the subduction interface; (h)
297 Coulomb failure stress changes on the volcanoes, indicated by numbers 1 to 12. Models (a-f and h)
298 are estimated at 10 km depth.

299 The results of the stress change analysis on the active faults of Ecuador reveal different
300 patterns of ΔCFS depending on the orientation of the receiver faults, being the receiver fault
301 orientation one of the most influential parameters on the stress change results. The most extended
302 lobes of ΔCFS correspond to faults with orientations N45-85, 180 (right hand rule orientation and
303 slip rake), right lateral NE-SW strike slip faults (Figure 5b), and N230-75, -90, NE-SW normal faults
304 (Figure 5d) while smaller lobes correspond to faults N15-35, 90 (Figure 5a) and its conjugate set
305 N195-35, -90 (Figure 5c), NNE-SSW thrust faults. Towards the south of the rupture the families
306 N110-75, -90 (E-W normal faults, Figure 5e) and N320-89, 0 (NW-SE left-lateral strike slip faults,
307 Figure 5f) are stressed. Negative values of ΔCFS (i.e. inhibition of fault movement) occur mainly
308 offshore and around Muisne.

309 The results of the stress change analysis on the subduction interface (Fig. 5g) show positive
310 values of ΔCFS downdip and updip the rupture. Negative values of ΔCFS are located on areas that
311 slipped during the earthquake. The small lobes of increment-decrement shown on the slab are
312 caused by small patches of slip obtained by the GPS-InSAR inversion methods and could be caused
313 by numerical artefacts. Moreover, these patches are located at depths higher than 50 km, and
314 consequently the influence on the seismic behaviour of the subduction interface would be limited.

315 The results of the stress analysis on the Ecuadorian volcanoes show that the 2016 earthquake
316 increased the normal stress by more than 0.1 bar on 3 of the volcanoes (numbers 1,6 and 4 in Figure
317 5h), with a maximum value of $\Delta\sigma$ of 0.202 bars at Tungurahua volcano (number 6 in Fig. 5h). The
318 volcanoes further north than Reventador (number 7 in Fig. 5h) show negative $\Delta\sigma$, indicating that
319 the 2016 earthquake induced a normal stress increase on the magma pathway of those volcanoes,
320 which might hinder magmatic activity.

321 4.5. Final maps

322 We have produced four final maps: seismic activity likelihood on mapped faults (Fig. 6a),
323 seismic activity likelihood on continental faults (Fig 6b), seismic activity likelihood on subduction
324 (Fig. 7) and volcanic activity likelihood on Ecuadorian volcanoes (Fig 8).

325 The map of seismic activity likelihood on mapped faults shows that faults with a high seismic
326 activity likelihood (red segments in Fig. 6a) are located in the Coastal Plain (region of Manabi)
327 between latitudes -1.5 and 0°N. These faults present values of $\Delta CFS > 1$ bar induced by the
328 Pedernales earthquake.

329 The map of seismic activity likelihood on continental faults shows a main lobe of Coulomb
330 Stress increment towards the southeast of the Pedernales rupture (Figure 6b), and a minor lobe
331 towards the northeast, the later caused mainly by the stress increment on NNE-SSW thrust faulting.

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335 **Figure 6. (a)** Map of seismic activity likelihood on mapped faults of Ecuador. Coloured segments

336 correspond to fault traces from [46]. Colours green – yellow – red indicate the likelihood of the fault

337 segment activation by the Pedernales earthquake; **(b)** Map of seismic activity likelihood on

338 continental faults.

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339 The map of seismic activity likelihood on the subduction interface shows areas of the slab with
 340 high likelihood (red areas in Fig. 7) located around the patches of coseismic slip. The regions of the
 341 slab with low seismic activity likelihood (green areas in Fig. 7) are found both on areas of coseismic slip
 342 and also away from the rupture.

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344 **Figure 7.** Map of seismic activity likelihood on subduction interface. The colour scale shows the
 345 likelihood of activation of the subduction interface by the Pedernales earthquake. Green (low
 346 likelihood) indicates areas with $\Delta CFS < 0.1$ bar, yellow (medium likelihood) indicates areas with
 347 $0.1 \text{ bar} \leq \Delta CFS \leq 1$ bar and red (high likelihood) indicates areas with $\Delta CFS > 1$ bar. 25-km slab
 348 iso-depth contour from [42] are indicated by the grey dashed lines. This map was calculated based
 349 on our source model. See Supplementary Fig. S5 for the map calculated using the earthquake source
 350 from the Global CMT focal mechanism.

351 The map of volcanic activity likelihood on Ecuadorian volcanoes shows that volcanoes with
 352 high activation likelihood (volcanoes inside the red area, i.e., numbers 1,4,6 in Fig. 8) are located to
 353 the southeast of the rupture while volcanoes with low activation likelihood (volcanoes inside the
 354 green area, i.e., numbers 7,9,10,11,12 in Fig. 8) are those located further north than latitude -0.17°N .

355 These maps should be interpreted in terms of increased likelihood for new seismic and
 356 volcanic events considering only the static stress changes produced by the Pedernales mainshock,
 357 but the occurrence of those events depends on the state of the system prior to the earthquake. Note
 358 that other phenomena not considered in this analysis may also influence the stress state of the crust
 359 and trigger or inhibit new seismic and volcanic events (see sections 5.2 and 5.3).

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362 **Figure 8.** Map of volcano activation likelihood on Ecuadorian volcanoes. Circled numbers indicate
 363 the Holocene volcanoes from http://volcano.si.edu/search_volcano.cfm. Colours indicate the
 364 likelihood of the volcano activation by the Pedernales earthquake, which depends on the value of
 365 the induced normal stress change ($\Delta\sigma$) on the volcano magma pathway. Green (low likelihood)
 366 indicates volcanoes with $\Delta\sigma < 0.01$ bar, yellow (medium likelihood) indicates volcanoes with 0.01
 367 bar $\leq \Delta\sigma \leq 0.1$ bar and red (high likelihood) indicates volcanoes with $\Delta\sigma > 0.1$ bar. This map was
 368 calculated based on our source model. See Supplementary Fig. S6 for the map calculated using the
 369 earthquake source from the Global CMT focal mechanism

370 5. Discussion

371 5.1. Models using the focal mechanism

372 We performed our calculations of static Coulomb failure stress changes associated with the
 373 Pedernales earthquake slip using as an alternative source the Global CMT focal mechanism. The
 374 interest of using such source is the promptness with which focal mechanisms are available (even a
 375 few minutes after the earthquake) compared to the source derived from InSAR and GPS data (days
 376 to weeks). Figure 9a shows the map of seismic activity likelihood on active faults of Ecuador
 377 calculated using the earthquake source from the Global CMT. Compared with the map created
 378 using our source (Fig. 6) the seismic activity likelihood on mapped faults is lower using the CMT
 379 source and fault segments with high seismic activity likelihood (red segments) are not the same in
 380 both maps.

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Figure 9. (a) Map of seismic activity likelihood on active faults of Ecuador calculated using the earthquake source from the Global CMT focal mechanism. The black rectangle delineates the source model; (b) Difference of Coulomb stress change on mapped faults. This map results from the difference between map in Fig. 6a and map in Fig. 9a.

387 We have computed the difference between both maps to identify their main similarities and
388 differences (Fig. 9b). The CMT model produce very similar results in faults far from the earthquake
389 source (white segments in Fig. 9b). For closer receivers the variation is however significant: for
390 example, the fault labelled X1 in Figures 6 and 9a shows a low seismic activity likelihood in the map
391 created using our source and a high seismicity value in the map created using the CMT source. A
392 similar case is the segment labelled X2 in Figures 6 and. 9a, with low values in the CMT map and
393 high values in the map derived from our source. This effect is common on every modelled
394 earthquake, in the near field the details and particularities of the slip distribution is one of the key
395 parameters that define the stress change field [51]; while in the far field the slip details are less
396 relevant and the approximate dimensions of the source and the earthquake magnitude is enough to
397 define a valid stress change field.

398 Since the static stress change is highly dependent on the slip distribution, the more data we can
399 add for the inversion of the source, the more reliable will be our final model. Using the focal
400 mechanism to produce a preliminary version of the maps can allow to have fast results after the
401 earthquake, but they should be updated using a better constrained source model when new
402 observations, particularly from seismological and geodetic networks that accurately observe the
403 earthquake process, are available.

404 5.2. Comparison of our final maps with seismic and volcanic events

405 We have compared seismic events in the period April 16th 2016 – February 18th 2018 with our
406 final maps. Using the seismic events from Instituto Geofísico Escuela Politécnica Nacional we have
407 separated events occurred in the subduction interface (selecting events at a distance ≤ 10 k from the
408 slab) from events occurred in continental faults (selecting events with distance to slab > 10 km and
409 depth < 15 km). Figures 10a and 10b show the events occurred in continental faults and in the
410 subduction interface, respectively, coloured according to the traffic light colour coding in Figures 6b
411 and 7. Red circles represent seismic events located in areas of high seismic activity likelihood (ΔCFS
412 > 1 bar), yellow circles represent seismic events in areas of medium seismic activity likelihood (0.1
413 $\text{bar} \leq \Delta CFS \leq 1$) and green circles represent seismic events in areas of low seismic activity likelihood
414 ($\Delta CFS < 0.1$ bar). We have quantified the number of events located on each “likelihood region”
415 (histograms in Fig. 10 c and d): for events occurred on the subduction interface (Figure 10d), 57 % of
416 the events occurred in areas of high or medium seismic activity likelihood. For events occurred at
417 continental faults (Figure 10c), only 35% of events occurred in areas of high or medium likelihood.
418 This can be explained by different factors: on the one hand, the seismic events analysed are not
419 relocated, and thus the final location of the events can vary from the one shown in Figure 10 a and
420 b. Moreover, our models only consider static stress changes induced by the Pedernales earthquake,
421 but other significant seismic events have occurred in the period April 2016 – February 2018 that
422 have also changed the stress state of the crust. For instance, the three largest events that have
423 occurred after the Pedernales earthquake (Supplementary Fig. S7) with Mw 6.3, 6.7 and 6.9, located
424 near Muisne, to the north of the main shock rupture, and may have triggered many of the seismic
425 events located in that area in Figs 10 a and b. Additionally, other processes apart from static stress
426 changes, such as dynamic stresses or postseismic phenomena, may influence the stress of the crust.
427 This will be discussed in section 5.3.

428 Regarding volcanic activity in Ecuador, according to Instituto Geofísico
429 (<http://www.igepn.edu.ec/informes-volcanicos>) at least two volcanoes in the Galapagos Islands
430 have shown volcanic activity or periods of unrest after the Pedernales earthquake: the Fernandina
431 volcano, in eruption since September 2017 and the Sierra Negra volcano, that shows seismic activity
432 since July 2017 and an uplift rate of 70 cm/yr
433 (<http://www.igepn.edu.ec/servicios/noticias/1539-informe-especial-sierra-negra-n-2-2017>).

434 However, Galápagos Islands are more than 1000 km away from the Pedernales earthquake source
435 and thus the static stress changes induced by the Pedernales earthquake on these volcanoes are too
436 small to trigger volcanic activity, although dynamic stresses associated to the elastic waves
437 propagation could be responsible. In continental Ecuador, three volcanoes present high activation

438 likelihood according to our geodetic-derived map (Fig8): Cotopaxi, Sangay and Tungurahua
 439 volcanoes. Using data from
 440 <https://volcano.si.edu/volcano.cfm?vn=352090> and <https://www.volcanodiscovery.com>, information
 441 about the volcanic activity of these volcanoes during the month after the earthquake (including ash
 442 emission, presence of thermal anomalies and significant seismic activity) was collected.

- 443 • Sangay volcano awoke one month before the earthquake (26th, April), according to reports
 444 about ash emission and thermal anomaly. Ash emission was ongoing during at least two
 445 months, and the thermal anomaly was recorded in the same period (12 May). After that, both
 446 ash emissions and thermal anomalies were intermittent through July 2016.
- 447 • In the vicinity of Cotopaxi volcano, two earthquakes of magnitude 3 and 3.1 occurred at a
 448 distance of 15 km from the volcano on April 17th 2016, the day after the Pedernales
 449 earthquake.
- 450 • Near Tungurahua volcano, five earthquakes were recorded between April 17th 2016 and
 451 May 19th 2016, with magnitudes ranging between 2.8 and 3.2 and distances between 21 to 33
 452 km away from the volcano.

453 Therefore, significant volcanic activity seems to have increased in these volcanoes around the date
 454 of the earthquake, suggesting a potential relationship between both phenomena.

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457 **Figure 10.** (a) Coloured circles represent seismic events in the period 16/04/2016 – 18/02/2018 from
 458 Instituto Geofísico Escuela Politécnica Nacional filtered for continental faults (distance to slab > 10
 459 km and depth < 15 km). Colours correspond to the traffic light colour code used in Figs. 6,7: red
 460 circles represent seismic events located in areas of high likelihood ($\Delta\text{CFS} > 1$ bar), yellow circles
 461 represent seismic events in medium likelihood areas ($0.1 \text{ bar} \leq \Delta\text{CFS} \leq 1$) and green circles represent
 462 seismic events in areas of low likelihood ($\Delta\text{CFS} < 0.1$ bar; (b) Seismic events in the period 16/04/2016
 463 – 18/02/2018 filtered for the subduction interface (distance to slab ≤ 10 km). Colours correspond to
 464 the traffic light colour code used in (a); (c) and (d) are the to accumulated histograms of frequency

465 (%) of seismic events after the mainshock on areas with the correspondent computed Coulomb
466 Stress change for the continental faults (b) and the subduction interface (c). The colour of the bar
467 indicates the likelihood index on a traffic light colour code of Fig. 7.

468 5.3. Potential and limits of the methodology

469 Nowadays several SAR satellites such as Sentinel-1A/B, ALOS-2, CSK, TSK, allow to produce
470 coseismic interferogramas relatively quick (from hours to few days) after an earthquake. The new
471 European Space Agency (ESA) Sentinel-1 constellation is particularly well adapted to this task,
472 since it acquires images globally every 6/12 days, that are distributed free of charge. In the next
473 years, several initiatives now in the testing phase to produce systematically interferograms should
474 be fully operational (e.g. GEP, LicS, ARIA, EPOS).

475 Coseismic GPS velocities are not globally available and their accessibility depends on different
476 factors, including the previous existence of a permanent and non-permanent GPS networks in the
477 zone. Although, more and more countries have a continuous GPS network, the data are rarely
478 public. However, some international initiatives exists to give access to GPS data, such as UNAVCO
479 consortium (<http://www.unavco.org/>) that provides Open Access GPS data with daily RINEX files
480 suitable for processing, although they mostly cover the United States and Caribbean zones.
481 Similarly, the European Plate Observing System will soon provide access to GNSS data in real time
482 over Europe (<https://www.epos-ip.org/tcs/gnss-data-and-products>).

483 Finite source models from InSAR and GNSS data can be performed using open-source
484 software tools such as RELAX (<https://geodynamics.org/cig/software/relax/>), Pyrocko
485 (<https://pyrocko.org/>), Defnode (<http://www.web.pdx.edu/~mccaf/defnode.html>). Including other
486 data in the inversion, such as seismological or tsunami data, can be helpful to constrain the offshore
487 part of the source model (e.g. [29]Ye et al. 2016). Our methodology can also be applied using other
488 earthquake sources, such as focal mechanisms or finite fault models from Global Seismic Network
489 (GSN) broadband waveforms (e.g.
490 <https://earthquake.usgs.gov/earthquakes/eventpage/us20005j32#finite-fault>), that are publicly
491 available after earthquakes.

492 One of the more time consuming step when applying this methodology is the compilation of
493 faults and volcanic elements to build the models. In the case of subduction earthquakes, the global
494 model for subduction geometries of [42] can be downloaded from
495 (<https://earthquake.usgs.gov/data/slab/>). Crustal faults are more difficult to obtain, and despite the
496 important efforts towards the systematization and compilation of active sources (GEM, Global
497 Active Faults: <https://github.com/GEMScienceTools/gem-global-active-faults>; SHARE, European
498 Database of Seismogenic Faults: http://diss.rm.ingv.it/share-edsf/SHARE_WP3.2_Database.html)
499 the completeness of the catalogue or the level of detail and the parameterization of the fault
500 elements usually requires further analysis. The existence of national publicly available databases
501 (e.g. the Quaternary Active Faults Database of Iberia, <http://info.igme.es/qafi/>, the New Zealand
502 Active Faults Database <http://data.gns.cri.nz/af/>) is a great advantage in these cases. However, the
503 main factor that determines the quality of the resulting maps is the quality, reliability and
504 completeness of the database (i.e. how reliable the faults and volcanoes parameters are). For
505 instance, unmapped faults can result in unexpected triggered earthquakes, such as the case of the
506 Christchurch earthquake [52].

507 The static Coulomb stress criterion, although a simplistic approach, is a powerful tool to
508 explain many fault and volcanic interactions and is issued as a tool for earthquake forecasting (e.g.
509 [7,19,53]. Several scientific softwares can be used to carry out these models (e.g. Coulomb 3.4 [45],
510 RELAX [54]).

511 Apart from the fault-fault or fault-volcano interactions analysed in this study, other
512 interactions can occur that could be taken into account, for example, aftershocks and postseismic
513 deformation (e.g. [14]), volcanic interactions (e.g. [55]) or coseismic-induced landslides (e.g. [56]).
514 Beyond the static stress changes estimated here, other mechanisms such dynamic stresses,
515 pore-fluid diffusion, and viscoelastic rebound can also be important for different time frames after

516 the earthquake. Additionally the incorporation of relevant aftershocks to the models, as well as
517 postseismic phenomena, can improve the hazard estimation and focus these tools towards an
518 operational forecasting system.

519 Finally, a close collaboration with the final user is critical to create functional and useful
520 products. The comprehension of our final maps was significantly improved thanks to the
521 constructive criticisms and specific proposals of the Geological Survey of Ecuador staff (Instituto
522 Nacional de Investigación Geológico Minero Metalúrgico, INIGEMM).

523 6. Conclusions

524 We present a methodology to evaluate earthquake-induced effects on neighbouring faults and
525 volcanoes and create easily understandable maps addressed to decision-makers managing the
526 post-earthquake situation. The first part of the method involves estimating the earthquake source
527 model from space geodetic data, the second part consist in using this model as input to calculate
528 static stress changes on tectonic and volcanic elements in the vicinity of the earthquake and the
529 third part is the creation of the final maps by synthetizing and simplifying the results for
530 non-experts.

531 We apply the methodology to the Mw 7.8, 2016 Pedernales earthquake, Ecuador. Using
532 Sentinel-1 InSAR and GPS data, we estimate the coseismic deformation field associated to the
533 Pedernales earthquake and invert this field to model the source. Then we calculate static stress
534 changes on the subduction interface, on the active continental faults of Ecuador and on the
535 volcanoes. The resulting maps show areas of high, medium or low seismic or volcanic activity
536 likelihood. When compared with seismic and volcanic event occurred after the Pedernales
537 earthquake, we found in general a good agreement, although some of the seismic and volcanic
538 events located in areas of low likelihood in our maps are probably due to other phenomena not
539 considered in our analysis, such as static stress changes from large aftershocks, dynamic stresses or
540 postseismic phenomena.

541 Our maps are useful to identify regions where new volcanic or seismic events are more likely
542 to happen taking into account the static stress changes produced by the mainshock. But our models
543 do not take into account the influence of other processes, such as dynamic stress changes produced
544 by the earthquake, postseismic phenomena or other tectonic and volcanic activity of the region.
545 Hence, other seismic or volcanic events could occur out of the critical areas depicted in the
546 proposed maps (red and yellow colours).

547 One of the main limitations of the methodology is the static stress approach, since other
548 earthquake-related processes can also influence the behaviour of faults and volcanoes (dynamic
549 stresses, pore-fluid diffusion, viscoelastic rebound). Also, an important limitation is the time
550 necessary to have a new SAR acquisition over the earthquake area, which usually takes several
551 days. This could be overcome using in the meantime the focal mechanism as a first-order
552 earthquake source.

553 Considering the open data policy of Sentinel-1 SAR data, the availability of tools for the
554 estimation of the earthquake source and the evaluation of static stress changes, the methodology
555 proposed here can be applied to earthquakes worldwide to quickly generate these maps after the
556 earthquake and update them when additional data (e.g. GPS data, coseismic interferograms from
557 other satellites, seismological and tsunami data) are available.

558

559 **Supplementary Materials:** The following are available online at www.mdpi.com/link, Figure S1: Observed,
560 modelled and residual GPS displacements, Figure S2: Modelled and residual InSAR displacements, Figure S3:
561 Smoothing coefficient for the optimal source model, Figure S4: Coulomb failure stress changes using the
562 Global CMT focal mechanism, Figure S5: Map of seismic activity likelihood on subduction interface using as
563 earthquake source the Global CMT focal mechanism, Figure S6: Map of volcanic activity likelihood on
564 Ecuadorian volcanoes using as earthquake source the Global CMT focal mechanism. Table S1: strike/dip/rake
565 values used for the Coulomb failure stress estimation on each family, Table S2: Dip and Azimuth of magma
566 paths of the five selected Ecuadorian volcanoes used for the estimation of the stress changes.

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575 **Author Contributions:** M.B.-P. and J.A.A.G. designed the study. O.M. and M.B.-P. processed InSAR data. A.S.
576 and M.P.L. processed and analysed GPS data. M.B.-P. modelled the earthquake source from InSAR and GPS
577 data. J.A.A.G. performed the Coulomb failure calculation and created the final maps. R.P.-L., M.B.-P. and K.C.
578 collected and analysed the catalogues of active faults and volcanoes. A.L., J.J.M.D., G.H., J.P.G., R.M.M.
579 analysed the final maps and provided feedback to improve them. J.A.A.G. and M.B.-P. prepared the figures.
580 M.B.-P. prepared the manuscript with advice and feedback from all team members.

581 **Conflicts of Interest:** The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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